

CHITOSAN/STARCH-BASED COMPOSITES OBTAINED BY TRADITIONAL SOLUTION METHOD AND VIA THERMOMECHANICAL PROCESSING

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Abstract: *Natural biopolymers such as chitosan and starch have demonstrated a huge potential in important and rapidly growing packaging applications. However, it is always challenging to create advanced biopolymer materials with enhanced physico-chemical and mechanical properties. In this study chitosan/starch-based samples were prepared by traditional solution method and via thermomechanical processing with the aim to obtain environmentally friendly materials for packaging. Different contents and types of polymers were incorporated into the compositions to obtain the material and to improve the physico-chemical and mechanical properties. Packaging materials should maintain moisture levels within the packaged product. Therefore, the moisture content, swelling degree and total soluble matter of the chitosan/starch-based samples were investigated in this study. It is well known that the natural polymers are typically highly hydrophilic and packaging produced with them can absorb water. Accordingly water contact angle was measured, which decreases when surface hydrophilicity is higher. To understand the effect of the ingredients on the wettability, contact angles were investigated for chitosan/starch-based samples. Moreover the physicochemical properties were investigated along with the mechanical properties to determine their potential uses for packaging applications.*

Keywords: biopolymers; starch; chitosan; packaging

1 MATERIALS AND METHODS

1. 1 *Materials*

Chitosan 20-300 cps (MW=50-190.000, DD $\geq$ 90%) was purchased from Sigma Aldrich, chitosan 30-100 cps (MW = 250.000, DD $\geq$ 90%) and chitosan 100-300 cps (MW = 890.000, DD $\geq$ 90%) were purchased from Glentham Life Sciences Ltd. ThreeTCl. Native potato starch (Przedsiębiorstwo Przemysłu Ziemniaczanego "Trzemeszno" Sp. z o. o.), native tapioca starch (Naturmind), glycerol (Eurochem BGS Sp. z o.o.), acetic acid 20% solution, lactic acid (purity $>$ 85%; density: 1,206 g mL⁻¹; Sigma Aldrich), chestnut extract (tannin Sevnica). Three types of lignin were used (dealkaline L0045 from Tokyo Chemical Industry, and Kraft (sulfate) ones: Lineo Classic and Lineo Classic W from Stora Enso). Three different poly(vinyl alcohol), PVA were used (Elvanol 71-30 (viscosity 27.0 – 33.0 mPa.s, Mw $\sim$ 100,000 fully hydrolyzed) was provided by Kuraray Europe GmbH, Mowiol 20-98 (viscosity 18.5-21.5 mPa.s, Mw $\sim$ 125,000, 98.0-98.8 mol% hydrolysis) purchased from Merck and Mowiol 8-88 – (viscosity 7-9 mPa.s, Mw $\sim$ 67,000, 86.7-88.7 mol% hydrolysis) were also purchased from Merck.

1. 2 *Sample preparation*

1. 2. 1 *Chitosan solutions*

All formulations were prepared by adding a specified amount of chitosan to the solution of water with glycerol and lactic acid by constant stirring (300 rpm; 24 h, room temperature) on a RCT magnetic stirrer (IKA, Staufen, Germany). After that a specified amount of the chestnut extract was added and the whole solution was homogenized (6000 rpm; 5 min; Ultra-Turrax T50 IKA). The obtained solutions were left overnight to get rid of the air bubbles formed during this process.

1. 2. 2 *Starch solutions*

All formulations were prepared by adding a specified amount of starch (table 2) to the solution of water with glycerol by constant stirring (300 rpm; 85 °C) on a water bath shaker (Julabo SW22, Germany). After that the solutions was homogenized (6000 rpm; 5 min; Ultra-Turrax T50 IKA). The obtained solutions were left overnight to get rid of the air bubbles formed during this process.

1. 2. 3 *Chitosan/starch-based samples obtained via casting method*

All formulations were prepared by mixing a specific amount of chitosan solution (1.2) and starch solution (1.3) according to the amounts in Table 3 and Table 4. The solutions were then homogenized (6000 rpm; 5 min; Ultra-Turrax

T50 IKA). The obtained solutions were left overnight to get rid of air bubbles formed during this process.

1. 2. 4 Chitosan/starch-based samples obtained via thermomechanical processing

The appropriate amount of glycerol was incorporated in the chitosan powder and manually mixed. Then, an adequate amount of acetic acid aqueous solution (20 wt.%) was added to the chitosan/glycerol mixture to obtain a paste with final chitosan concentration of 30 wt.%. Then starch, lignin and PVA were introduced. The mixtures were then mechanically blended in a HaakePoly-Lab QC Reomix 600 internal batch mixer at 80 °C for 4 min, with a rotor speed of 40 rpm. Finally, the resulting materials were firstly hot-pressed at 110 °C, 250 bar pressure for 7 min and immediately cooled at room temperature, in the press, for 2 min.

Figure 1: Chitosan/starch-based composites obtained by traditional solution method

Figure 2: Chitosan/starch-based composites obtained via thermomechanical processing